

Formation of Korean Pronunciation Skills of Uzbek Speakers

Kamarova Maftuna Umar qizi

Teacher of the department of Korean philology, Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Abstract. *Pronunciation is one of the most important aspects of learning a foreign language. Because the level of mastery of a language is shown through communication in that language. The main foundation of communication is the formation of pronunciation skills. Therefore, in this article, Uzbek students and teachers of the Korean language, who are learning Korean, have ideas about how to master the pronunciation rules of the Korean language and how to use them in the process of conversation.*

Key words: *Korean language, pronunciation, competencies, vowel sound, consonant sound, syllable, phonetics.*

1. Introduction.

Human communication skills consist of the ability to express one's thoughts, such as speaking, writing, and comprehension skills, including: listening and reading. It is impossible to single out which of them is more important in the communication process. But if we have the ability to express one's opinion, communication takes place more in speaking than writing, and the ability of listening and understanding is more actively involved in communication than reading skills.

2. Main part.

The importance of forming pronunciation skills. As mentioned above, speaking and listening comprehension are also indicators of how well you know a foreign language. Therefore, it is necessary for educators to form systematic pronunciation skills that play an important role in the process of teaching speaking and listening comprehension, which are important functions of communication. The situations that occur when there are mistakes in pronunciation are as follows:

- 1) No matter how well a Korean language learner has mastered the grammar of this language, if he pronounces words incorrectly during a conversation, he will not be able to convey clearly the idea he wants to convey to the interlocutor. For example, when the word "자금 (money)" is pronounced as "저금 (to save)" and the word "반친구 (groupmate)" is pronounced as "방친구 (roommate)", there is a misunderstanding in the content of the conversation.
- 2) Such incorrect pronunciations cause difficulties for the listener not only during communication, but also during listening comprehension. In many cases, Korean language learners are also unable to understand clearly when they hear Korean words. For example, hearing the word "여권 (passport)" as "여관 (place to sleep)" or hearing the word "튼튼하다 (strong)" as "똥똥하다 (fat)" is observed.
- 3) Since there are some situations when the learners of this language write words in a foreign language and as they pronounce them, spelling mistakes also occur in the writing rules - 맞춤법.

For example, spelling mistakes such as writing the word "머리 (head)" as "모리" and the word "사귀다 (get to know)" as "사기다" are common among learners of language who have problems with pronunciation.

- 4) In the process of reading, the shortcomings in pronunciation are seriously manifested. Especially when reading aloud, the student himself faces difficulty in understanding the content of what he is reading without being able to deliver the content clearly and comprehensibly.

As mentioned above, since pronunciation directly affects all forms of communication such as speaking, listening, writing, and reading, teaching pronunciation in Korean language education is the foundation of quality education. A question arises here. Since pronunciation is so important, what should be the limit of teaching Korean pronunciation? Of course, it is difficult to completely change the pronunciation of language learners to the clear and natural pronunciation of that nation. The reason is that language learners are directly influenced by their native language. In particular, the situations above are observed among Uzbek learners who are learning the Korean language. As a result of the fact that most of the Uzbek learners study the Korean language in a fixed period, in a planned state, there is a limit to learn the pronunciation of the Korean language. This situation, of course, is more typical for language courses or independent learners. Studying Korean philology in higher education, institutions learn Korean pronunciation rules in detail from the subject of "Korean Phonetics", which teaches pronunciation rules, because they are trained as experts. But even this will not be enough to speak Korean very clearly and understandably.

Tips for achieving natural pronunciation in Korean.

First of all, when starting to learn the letters of the Korean language, the vowels and consonants that are unique to the Korean language, the characteristics of each of the diphthongs, and the pronunciation standards, which are different from the Uzbek language, should be explained in detail. After that, it is important to pay special attention to syllables, their formation, structure, and pronunciation. For example, an open syllable in Korean does not differ from an open syllable in Uzbek, but there are differences in the closed syllables of the two languages. Because the Korean language is written in a unique way, the last consonant of a closed syllable in Korean is called "badchim (pole)" and is written on the second line, i.e. from below. There are 19 consonant letters in "badchim" and they are pronounced with 7 different sounds. These are: "k (ㄱ, ㅋ, ㆁ), n (ㄴ), t (ㄷ, ㅌ, ㄴ, ㅌ, ㅊ, ㅌ, ㅊ, ㅌ), l/r (ㄹ), m (ㅁ), p (ㅂ, ㅍ), ng (ㅇ) are sounds.

At the next stage, it is necessary for students to thoroughly master the rules of Korean phonetics. Korean language learners who have mastered the rules well can read, speak, and also understand the listening comprehension process by following the pronunciation rules. And lastly, the change of tone depending on the content of the sentence is also unique in the Korean language. Therefore, it is advisable to teach the pronunciation of the indicative sentence with the tone of the indicative sentence and the interrogative sentence with the tone of the interrogative sentence step by step.

3. Conclusion.

Although the Uzbek and Korean languages belong to the Altai language family, their similarities can be seen in their grammar, sentence structure, etc., but the uniqueness of both languages is inevitable in pronunciation and speech. The desire to be able to speak Korean fluently and clearly is the goal of every student who wants to learn this language, and every teacher who is currently teaching this language. To achieve this goal, the tips and suggestions above on how to improve Korean pronunciation will help.

List of used literature:

1. Kamarova M.U., "On the basics, problems and tasks of Korean language education in South Korea", 2023.

2. Jiyoung Kwak, et al., “The Reality of Korean Language Teaching Methods”, Yonsei University Press Center, 2018.
3. Myung-Kwang Kim, “Korean language curriculum theory as a foreign language”, Communication, 2023.
4. Ki-sim Nam, et al., “New Standard Korean Grammar”, Korean Culture History, 2023.
5. Woo Hyeong-Sik et al., “Field-centered Korean language teaching method”, Hangeul Park, 2019.